

Characterising COVID-19 Morbidity Dynamic Pattern across Neighbourhoods in New York City

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Summary

This research implements partitioning around medoids (PAM) clustering algorithm on the dynamic time warping (DTW) distance calculated from the weekly variation of COVID-19 testing positive rate, aiming to profile and understand the dynamics of viral morbidity among neighbourhoods in New York City (NYC). With the specific focus on the residential usage neighbourhood tabulation areas (NTAs) in NYC, we classify 197 NTAs into six clusters characterising different COVID-19 dynamics. Based on their salient features, we interpret each cluster and anticipate possible future directions of this work.

KEYWORDS: COVID-19, Morbidity Dynamics, Time Series Analysis, Neighbourhood Disparities

Introduction

The ongoing COVID-19 pandemic has brought catastrophic consequences for morbidity, mortality, and economic activity (Cutler & Summers, 2020; Nicola et al., 2020; Staadegaard et al., 2021). As of October 30 2021, more than 245 million cases and nearly 5 million fatalities associated with COVID-19 had been reported globally (Dong et al., 2020).

Existing retrospective studies related to COVID-19 have mainly concentrated on elucidating the spatiotemporal transmission pattern at the local or regional level (Cheng, Lu, et al., 2021; Ma et al., 2021); estimating viral transmissibility among communities and thereby assessing the effectiveness of non-pharmaceutical interventions (Arroyo-Marioli et al., 2021; Cheng, Zhong, et al., 2021); predicting possible pandemic outcomes from sophisticated machine learning models (Barda et al., 2020; Yan et al., 2020); and exploring associations between COVID-19 morbidity or mortality and multidimensional attributes (Islam et al., 2020; Warren & Skillman, 2020). While the majority of these studies analysed different COVID-19 indicators at a relatively static timestamp, limited studies examined the (dis-)similarities in the overall dynamics of morbidity patterns over relatively small zonal geographies (e.g., neighbourhood areas). Such (dis-)similarities among neighbourhoods may be considered as an inequity that should not be neglected since it has the potential to exacerbate existing health disparities further and thereby widen social inequality. Additionally, developing a clear understanding of variations in viral morbidity dynamics across neighbourhoods facilitates the implementation of targeted interventions, promoting evidence-based policymaking.

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Within this context, this paper employs an analytical framework based on Dynamic Time Warping (DTW) and Partitioning Around Medoids (PAM) to conduct a time series clustering analysis of neighbourhood morbidity dynamics. Our framework has been applied to the weekly averaged COVID-19 testing positive rates sourced from 197 residential Neighbourhood Tabulation Areas (NTAs) in New York City (NYC) to demonstrate its utility in differentiating nuances in COVID-19 morbidity dynamics amongst neighbourhood areas.

Study Area

There are 262 NTAs in the extent of NYC, 197 of which are defined as residential usage. In this study, only residential NTAs were utilised as the target observations (see **Figure 1**). NTAs³ are medium-sized statistical geographies that are used for tabulating the Decennial Census and American Community Survey (ACS). They are constructed by aggregating multiple small geographies (i.e., census tracts) while taking geographic specificity and statistical reliability into account. Although NTAs borders are not strictly recognised as the boundaries of neighbourhoods, they are designed to provide close statistical representations of them (NYC Planning, 2021).

Data Description and Pre-processing

Weekly averaged COVID-19 testing positive rates were utilised to represent the dynamic evolution of COVID-19 transmission across neighbourhoods in NYC, which were obtained from the NYC Health COVID-19 open data portal⁴. The study period ranged from 08-08-2020 to 25-09-2021, lasting 60 weeks. The absolute number of confirmed cases was not employed in this study because existing studies have identified its positive association with the amount of testing, which varies in both time and space (Kaashoek & Santillana, 2020) and thereby increases data bias.

Given the COVID-19 case data were only available at the modified ZIP Code Tabulation Areas (MODZCTA) geography, we adopted the area-weighted average method to aggregate COVID-19 information into the NTA level, calculated by using **Eq. 1**. Heatmaps in **Figure 1** illustrate the dynamic evolution of testing positive rates in each of the 197 NTAs throughout the study period. It is visible that the overall COVID-19 morbidity pattern in NYC was bimodal: the first wave occurred between November 2020 and April 2021, and the second wave occurred from August 2021 to the end of the study period. While the majority of NTAs followed this bimodal pattern, several of them demonstrated spatial and temporal heterogeneity, reiterating the necessity of this research. After assembling the time series dataset, the z-score method (**Eq.2**) was used to standardise the data prior to clustering analysis.

$$\bar{x} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i * w_i)}{\sum_{i=1}^n w_i} \quad 1$$

Eq. 1 \bar{x} is the weighted mean; x_i is an original value; w_i is the weight which is the proportion of the area occupied by a specific MODZCTA in NTA.

$$z_i = \frac{x_i - \mu}{\sigma} \quad 2$$

Eq. 2 where z_i is the standardised value, x_i is an original value, μ is the mean of x_i , and σ is the standard deviation from the mean.

³ On average, a NTA contains 40,000 people (NYC Planning, 2021)

⁴ <https://github.com/nychealth/coronavirus-data>

Figure 1 Heatmaps of residential NTAs' weekly averaged COVID-19 positive rate in NYC (08-08-2020 to 25-09-2021), grouped by boroughs (i.e., Bronx, Brooklyn, Manhattan, Queens, and Staten Island).

Methodology

To systematically examine the dynamic evolution of COVID-19 morbidity across neighbourhoods in NYC, we applied an analytical framework configured by DTW distance and PAM clustering algorithm to conduct a time-series clustering analysis.

DTW, introduced by Berndt & Clifford (1994), is one of the widely used algorithms for evaluating (dis-)similarity between a given number of temporal sequences. The utility of this technique has been approved by its widespread applications in a variety of research disciplines, including but not limited to speech and movement recognition, economic and financial analysis, remote sensing imagery, and urban functionality research (Chen et al., 2017; D'Urso et al., 2021; Guo et al., 2020; Ismail et al., 2020). With the consideration of shape information, this distance function utilises nonlinear warping to identify the optimal alignment between time series through stretching or compressing parts of their segments (Izakian et al., 2015; Müller, 2007). Although most of the existing studies have adopted the Euclidean distance metric due to its convenient implementation and computational efficiency, DTW distance has been recognised as superior for clustering time series, especially under the circumstances the time axis is distorted (Ratanamahatana & Keogh, 2004). **Figure 2** compares the difference between the DTW (black dash line) and Euclidean measures (red vertical lines) in terms of the trend of COVID-19 positive rates at two randomly selected NTAs. The result exemplifies that the superiority of DTW distance over the Euclidean distance in terms of robustness, as the former considers the influence of multiple timestamps, whilst the latter 'statically' calculates the distance between the two same dates.

Figure 2 Comparison between DTW and Euclidean measure at two examples NTAs (QN0601 and BK0802). DTW distances were represented by dash lines; Euclidean distances were represented by red vertical lines.

Following the calculation of the DTW distance, we applied the PAM clustering technique to segment 197 NTAs in NYC based on their COVID-19 transmission patterns. PAM, developed by (Kaufman & Rousseeuw, 1990), is one of the representative algorithms of the k-medoids clustering aiming to partition a dataset into a predefined number of groups (k) by minimising dissimilarities within each group (Reynolds et al., 2004). This clustering algorithm is a more robust alternative to commonly-used k-means clustering because it is less susceptible to the existence of extreme values in the data (Jin & Han, 2017). Additionally, the Dunn index, introduced by Dunn (1974), was utilised to determine k before implementing PAM. When the index is maximised, the optimum k is obtained. Based on this index, six was finally selected as the optimal number of clusters.

Results and interpretations

To evaluate the characteristics of the PAM-generated time series clusters, index scores were computed for the timestamp and displayed within each cluster in **Figure 3**. Such scores indicate the (over-) underrepresentation of a specific timestamp in comparison to the NYC median value (100)⁵. Furthermore, the spatial distribution of these clusters is illustrated in **Figure 4**. According to these visualisations, each group can be profiled based on its most conspicuous characteristics.

NTAs categorised in Cluster 1 are prevalently located in southern parts of Staten Island, Brooklyn, and Queens, recognised as the worst-hit areas in NYC since their positive rates were constantly and considerably higher than the NYC median throughout the study period. Among the above-median fluctuations, two outbreak spikes can be observed. The first peak occurred in October 2020, and the second one occurred between July and August 2021.

The overall COVID-19 positive rates in NTAs from Cluster 2 gradually diminished during the

⁵ For example, an index score 50 would thereby equate to a rate that is half the median, and 200 would be double.

research period – from significantly high to relatively moderate. Between August and September 2020, the highest positive rate of these NTAs was about double that of the NYC median, followed by steady reduction over time to the variations around the median baseline. These neighbourhoods are predominately situated in southwest Brooklyn and the central Bronx, with a scattering in the outskirts of Queens.

Positive rates recorded in Cluster 3 NTAs maintained about a quarter higher than the median baseline. These neighbourhoods are scattered across the five boroughs of NYC except Manhattan, with specific agglomerations in northern Staten Island, eastern Bronx, and central Queens. A similar steady morbidity pattern was also detected in NTAs from Cluster 5. However, the index value remained around 25% lower than the baseline. As such, these neighbourhoods may be recognised as the less severely affected areas of NYC, with a concentration in northern Manhattan, northeast and northwest Queens, north Bronx, and central Brooklyn.

NTAs grouped in Cluster 4 are primarily located in Brooklyn and Queens, without obvious spatial agglomerations. These neighbourhoods experienced a continuous rise in COVID-19 positive rates, reaching a peak between May and June 2021, when the rate was nearly 50% higher than the NYC median. Although oscillations occurred after this spike, the overall positive rate was consistently greater than the baseline value during the remaining period.

Despite a sharp rise between June and August 2021, NTAs from Cluster 6 exhibited the least severe pandemic effect as compared to other NTAs in NYC, which is manifested by the positive rates continuously lower than the median baseline throughout the study period. These NTAs are predominately agglomerated in Manhattan, particularly the central and southern portions (i.e., the most prosperous areas in NYC), with the second-largest concentration in Brooklyn city centre.

Conclusion and future directions

In this study, we applied a time series clustering framework based on DTW and PAM to differentiate neighbourhoods in NYC based on the temporal COVID-19 morbidity pattern. Six clusters were generated from the clustering analysis. Given the similar overall COVID-19 bimodal patterns in NYC, the results explicitly demonstrated that there were distinctive differences in the viral transmission patterns amongst neighbourhood areas, accompanied by the presence of spatial homogeneity (e.g., most neighbourhoods in Manhattan were categorised as least-hit areas). As such, one of the viable directions for extending this study is to conduct a more in-depth analysis of such spatial and temporal disparities. For instance, future research may explore the multidimensional contexts of these neighbourhoods (e.g., socioeconomic, demographic, and environmental factors) to unfold the underlying reasons for their dynamic similarity or dissimilarity. Moreover, since we utilised open data as input to demonstrate the utility of our analytical framework, this paradigm may readily be used in many other urban settings to analyse the spatiotemporal disparities of COVID-19 morbidity and mortality.

Figure 3 Dynamic variation of the index scores for each of the six generated clusters; NYC median = 100 (red horizontal line)

Figure 4 Spatial Distribution of six clusters (NTA level). NA indicates non-residential NTAs.

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